

Monitoring air pollution using infrared photoacoustic spectra of organic vapours[†]

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CO₂ laser excited photoacoustic (PA) spectra of methanol, ethanol and trichloroethylene in the vapour phase have been recorded in the 9.6 μm and 10.6 μm spectral regions. A comparison with conventional IR and Raman spectra of these compounds shows that peaks in the PA spectra correspond to rotational contours of the vibrational bands with a limit of resolution better than 0.04 μm . The photoacoustic spectral peaks can be used in qualitative as well as quantitative spectrochemical analysis of air samples and can detect trace amounts (a few parts in 10⁶) of these chemicals in air.

Infrared spectroscopy plays a vital role in monitoring the presence of pollutant gases and vapours in the atmosphere. Except for homonuclear diatomic molecules such as F₂ and Cl₂, every air pollutant has an infrared absorption in the spectral region 2.5–25 μm . The application of infrared (IR) absorption spectroscopy to pollutants is, however, limited by the amounts of energy available from the optical sources. In conventional IR spectroscopy, blackbody sources coupled to grating or prism monochromators, have been used to provide beams of narrow spectral width. These sources are inadequate to provide sufficient power over a narrow spectral region ($\sim 0.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), thereby leading to poor sensitivity and specificity of detection of the pollutants. The availability of infrared lasers circumvents the inadequacies of conventional sources and has led to much activity in monitoring air quality as well as detection of polluting gases and vapours^{1, 2}. Photoacoustic spectroscopy in combination with laser sources, has been found to be a very effective technique of detecting extremely weak IR absorption in gases^{3–6}. Concentrations of harmful chemicals above a certain level in air pose serious health hazards. This has created the need for new environmental monitoring methods. In the present work, we employed a CO₂ laser for the purpose of detecting small concentrations of methanol, ethanol and trichloroethylene in the vapour phase. The infrared spectra of these organic compounds are well known and their vibrational band intensities in the 9.6 and 10.6 μm regions were monitored as a function of concentration.

Experimental

The experimental set-up for recording the normalized photoacoustic (PA) spectra of organic vapours is schematically shown in Fig. 1. Two separate borosilicate glass cells

with KBr windows were used, one for the organic vapour and the other for carbon black sample. To record the spectrum of the vapour, the PA cell (10 cm \times 2 cm dia, fitted with a microphone) was evacuated down to 0.2 Torr after closing stop-cocks at the two ends of the cell. The liquid phase organic sample was in a small round bottomed flask with a

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of experimental set-up for recording photoacoustic spectra of vapour samples : (1) CO₂ laser, (2) attenuators, (3) chopper, (4, 5) Pirani gauge, (6) KBr window, (7) microphone, (8) pre-amplifier, (9) lock-in amplifier.

grounded joint attached to the inlet of the PA cell and the connecting stopcock was opened. Once the cell was filled with organic vapour, the stopcock was closed. The outlet of the PA cell was opened and the cell evacuated. This purging was repeated thrice and finally the PA cell was filled with organic vapour with its outlet stopcock closed. The inlet stopcock was open and the stabilized vapour pressure in

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the PA cell was recorded. At this point, the inlet stopcock as well as the stopcock connecting the cell to the pressure gauge were closed and the PA spectrum of the vapour was recorded manually by reading the microphone signal at the lock-in amplifier corresponding to each wavelength of the rotationally tunable CO₂ laser. The PA cell containing carbon black sample was 5 cm × 2 cm dia. and the microphone was fitted close to the KBr window on the far side from the CO₂ laser source. This KBr window had a thick coating of lampblack which absorbed the laser radiation and provided reference signals at the microphone that was recorded at the panel of the lock-in amplifier corresponding to each wavelength of the rotationally tunable CO₂ laser. The PA signals of pure organic vapours as well as their mixtures at each wavelength of the CO₂ laser output were divided by the corresponding signals from carbon black to obtain the

Fig. 2. Normalized vapour phase photoacoustic spectra of (a) methanol, (b) ethanol and (c) trichloroethylene.

Fig. 3. Normalized photoacoustic spectra of mixed vapours of ethanol and methanol in varying proportions (methanol : ethanol).

normalized spectra shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

The rotational line tunable CW CO₂ laser (model 8822 of M/s Ultra Lasertech Inc., Canada) had a maximum power of 15 W which was reduced to 50 mW by using ZnSe attenuators to prevent saturation effects in the spectra. Power of the laser radiation was measured by a pyroelectric power meter (model RKP 360 of M/s Laser Precision Corporation, USA). The unfocused laser beam entering the PA cell had a diameter of 6 mm and its emission wavelength (at each rotational line) was monitored by a CO₂ spectrum analyzer (model 16A of M/s Optical Engineering, USA). Some of the rotational lines did not lase. The CO₂ laser beam was chopped at 22 Hz by a mechanical chopper (model SR540 of Stanford Research Inc., USA) before entering the PA cell. The absorption of CO₂ laser radiation by the sample is followed by non-radiative decay causing pressure fluctuations

in the PA cell which were detected by a sensitive microphone fitted in the airlight PA cell. The output of the microphone was fed to an indigenous preamplifier and the amplified signal was fed to the lock-in-amplifier (model 186A, EG&G Princeton Applied Research, USA). The reference to the lock-in was fed from the chopper and the resulting PA signal was read from the panel meter of the former at each wavelength of CO₂ laser emission.

Liquid samples of methanol, ethanol and trichloroethylene (Ranbaxy) were used with spectral purity of 99.59, 99.5 and 98.8%, respectively. The saturated vapour pressures of methanol, ethanol and trichloroethylene at 300 K are 138, 69 and 77 Torr, respectively⁷.

The vapour pressure in the PA cell for mixed vapours was obtained from the equation,⁸

$$p = x_1 p_1 + x_2 p_2 + x_3 p_3 \quad (1)$$

where p is the total vapour pressure of the mixture and p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots are vapour pressures of individual compounds with their respective mole fractions x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots . The mole fraction of the i -th compound in the mixture is given by

$$x_i = V_i / \sum V_i \quad (2)$$

where V_i is the volume of the i -th compound in the mixture. The normalized PA spectra of a mixture containing methanol and ethanol vapour with varying proportions by volume of methanol and ethanol in the liquid mixture are shown in Fig. 3.

Results and discussion

Analysis of photoacoustic spectra :

A perusal of Fig. 2 shows that methanol vapour exhibits two peaks at 9.62 and 9.66 μm corresponding to 1040 and 1035 cm^{-1} in frequency units, the latter being stronger in intensity. The PA spectrum of ethanol vapour also exhibits two peaks at 9.52 (1050) and 9.59 μm (1043 cm^{-1}) of which the peak at 1050 cm^{-1} is stronger of the two. There are three peaks in the spectrum of trichloroethylene vapour at 10.54 (949), 10.63 (941) and 10.72 μm (933 cm^{-1}) of which the central peak (941 cm^{-1}) is the strongest.

The two peaks at 1040 and 1035 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of methanol vapour constitute the rotational contour of the C–O stretching vibration observed at 1034 cm^{-1} under low resolution^{9,10}. Similarly, the two peaks at 1050 and 1043 cm^{-1} are rotational contour peaks of C–O stretching vibration of ethanol observed at 1050 cm^{-1} under low resolution¹⁰. The three peaks in the spectrum of trichloroethylene represent the rotational contour of an umbrella type out of

plane vibration (ν_{12}) in which the two carbon atoms move out on one side of the molecular plane and hydrogen as well as the chlorine atoms move on the opposite side. This vibration has been observed under low resolution at 940 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectrum and at 947 cm^{-1} in the Raman spectrum¹¹.

Variation of PA signal with vapour pressure :

The partial pressure p_i of the vapour of i -th compound in a mixture is determined from the relation,

$$p_i = x_i p_s \quad (3)$$

where x_i is the mole fraction of the compound as defined in eqn. (2) and p_s is its saturated vapour pressure as given in Experimental section. Since the vapour in the PA cell has no contact with the liquid in the bulb during experimental measurements, the value of p_i determined from eqn. (3) remains unchanged even at slightly increased temperatures that may result due to heating effect of the laser radiation.

The relative strength of the PA signal was determined from the height of the photoacoustic peak corresponding to a particular partial pressure of the vapour. Variations of PA signals with partial pressure of methanol at the two peaks corresponding to $\lambda_1 = 9.66 \mu\text{m}$ and $\lambda_2 = 9.62 \mu\text{m}$ are shown

Fig. 4. Variation of photoacoustic signal with concentration of methanol at $\lambda_1 = 9.66$ and $\lambda_2 = 9.62 \mu\text{m}$. The horizontal line represents ratio of signals at λ_1 and λ_2 .

in Fig. 4. The ratio of PA signals at λ_1 and λ_2 corresponding to a particular partial pressure (Fig. 4) gives a horizontal line, indicating that there is no interference from the vapour of ethanol in the mixture.

The well resolved rotational peaks in the vibrational spectra of vapours of methanol, ethanol and trichloroethylene (Fig. 2) show that CO₂ laser based photoacoustic detection of these compounds can be easily done in a polluted air sample. The variation of PA signals of methanol with its partial pressure in a mixture exhibits monotonic increase with increase in pressure and a calibration curve can be easily

Table 1. Comparison of observed vibrational frequencies in PA spectra and the IR/Raman data of pure organic compounds

Compd.	PA peak ^a cm ⁻¹	Rel. int. ^b	IR frequency cm ⁻¹	Assignment
CH ₃ OH	1035	S	1034	C–O stretch ^{c,d}
	1040	M		
C ₂ H ₅ OH	1043	VS	1050	C–O stretch ^d
	1050	M		
C ₂ HCl ₃	933	VS	940 (IR)	Umbrella type o-p vibration ^e
	941	VS	947 (Raman)	
	949	S		

^aRot. contour. ^bS = strong; VS = very strong; M = medium.

^cRef. 9. ^dRef. 10. ^eRef. 11.

drawn for polluted air samples to get quantitative estimate of methanol. In the present experiments it is estimated that at atmospheric pressures the limit of detecting the polluting vapours is a few parts in 10⁶.

It is seen from Fig. 2 that simultaneous presence of methanol and ethanol in air can be detected by CO₂ laser photoacoustic measurements although their vibrational bands fall in the 9.6 μm region. This is possible due to highly resolved rotational lines of the CO₂ laser radiation which generate PA signals.

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